

ANALYSIS OF BUSINESS STRATEGIES OF INTERNATIONAL CARD SCHEMES IN THE NATIONAL MARKET USING GAME THEORY

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Abstract: *In the modern world, companies cannot effectively operate or survive in the market without utilizing cashless payment systems. The most common form of non-cash payment is through payment cards. In this paper, we analyze business strategies and strategic moves applied by international card schemes on the national market of payment cards, in order to eliminate competition. National card schemes are present only in the market of the countries where they were created, while international card schemes operate worldwide. There are notable differences in their equity capital, annual revenue, and consequently, their budgets for research and development. Additionally, many national card schemes are motivated not only by profit but also by societal interests, which further reduces their negotiating potential. The national market of card payments can be viewed as a zero-sum game because the gain of one card scheme represents the loss of another; that is, the others in that market. The question arises as to what strategies card schemes use to improve their market share. This paper presents several strategies employed by international card schemes to maintain a dominant market position, and several games are modeled to analyze such market situations.*

Keywords: *International card schemes, national card schemes, payment cards, game theory, strategies.*